

ELEMENTS OF GREEN ARCHITECTURE DESIGN AS A COMBINATION OF GREEN WALL, ECO SCULPTURE AND LAND ART

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Abstract: *The paper shows positive examples of the use of green architecture design elements through the synthesis of aesthetic and utilitarian principles that fulfill the premises of sustainability as a necessary tendency of contemporary architecture. Starting from the definition of green architecture and its emerging forms that preceded the modern ones, we deal with the visual aspect of biophilic architecture through examples of green walls; suggest implementation of eco-sculpture and explain its peculiarity in the urban environment. The arrangement of gardens, parks and children's play areas also requires a transformation that can be achieved through the synthesis of landscape architecture and land art. As contemporary urban architecture meets the needs of modern society that strives for a healthy and clean environment and sustainability, the implementation of eco-art objects in modern architectural solutions is recommended as a harmonious combination of aesthetic and utilitarian needs of an ecologically conscious society.*

Keywords: *green architecture, green wall, eco-sculpture, land art, environmental art*

1. INTRODUCTION

Green architecture seems to be a new tendency of modern architecture though we have testimonies of some ancient chronicles that speak about living plants and water springs in famous Hanging gardens of Babylon about 700 years B. C. We found it merely logical that for centuries mankind has always wanted to reach both security and comfort of residence and keep in touch with abundant nature as a reminiscence of Paradise [1]. Wilderness seemed something opposite to human civilization, yet the freshness and abundance that plants exude caused a constant need for people to implement plant and water surfaces in their immediate living environment – in the form of gardens, atriums, plant terraces, pergolas, etc. From antiquity to the present day, living architecture has become a multidisciplinary field, in which the professional scopes and knowledge of architects, designers or mural painters, landscape architects, botanists, ecologists, etc. intertwine and complement each other. With the emergence of the modern industrial city, today home to more than half of the world's population, planners, designers and urbanists are becoming advocates of turning to plants – green infrastructure – as a key strategy for ensuring cleaner air and water, while improving environmental quality, human health and mental well-being [2].

Ecological art, environmental art or eco-art are almost synonyms. The term *environment art* describes artworks made using nontraditional materials or integrated into a specific natural setting. While environmental art is similar in concept, it typically carries a distinct environmental message or intention. As a result, environmental art is often linked to themes of environmental responsibility and ethics [3]. When defining *land art*, we usually think of *Earthworks*, artworks of huge dimensions, such as *Spiral Jetty* by Robert Smithson or *Double negative* by Michael Heizer. The Land art movement arose in the '60-ies and '70-ies by some pioneering artists who tried to, in a conceptual way, evoke ecological problems making huge structures of stone and soil in far-away sites. They also opposed commercial and materialistic regards to artwork which then became a structure in nature, not possessed by anyone, without financial worth, presented to the public through photos and videos. Nevertheless, despite great dimensions and monumental form of such Earthworks made by American artists, there are small and ephemeral artworks that are also considered to be land art forms, created by some of European land artists, such as structures made of leaves, branches, icicles, snow, etc. The most significant in this form of land art are the works of British artists Andy Goldsworthy and Richard Long. In terms of art that restores nature, a special place is occupied by *social sculpture* as an ecological project of the German artist Joseph Beuys. In this text, we choose to speak of land art made of solid material and of a more permanent character, i.e. forms made on the ground that can be seen as solid structures that complement the landscape aesthetically and functionally.

2. ELEMENTS OF ECOLOGICAL ART APPLICABLE IN GREEN ARCHITECTURE

2.1. Green Walls – Living Plant Murals

Greening of vertical wall surfaces means growing plants on, along or next to the wall by planting plants in soil, containers or vertical hydroponic systems. Vertical green areas on the walls of buildings are today known as *vertical gardens*, *green walls*, *living walls*, *bio walls* or *plant walls* (fr. *mur vegetal*) or, scientifically, vertical vegetated complex walls (VCWs). [4] There are two primary categories of green walls: green façades and living walls. These systems can be applied to both the interior and exterior of buildings. Green façades involve climbing plants that grow from the ground and spread across the surface of a wall. In contrast, living walls feature plants that grow in soil or fabric systems attached directly to the wall, rather than rooting in the ground, and they require an integrated irrigation system to provide water and nutrients. Green façades are exclusively used on exterior walls, while living walls can be installed on either interior or exterior surfaces. [5]

The history of vertical green surfaces goes from already mentioned *Hanging gardens of Babylon*, through the ancient Greeks and Romans who used to train grape vines along the walls of their villas. In the Middle Ages, manors and castles with climbing roses were the symbols of secret gardens. One astonishing phenomenon in green architecture is the green facades designed by Hundertwasser back in the 1980s in Vienna. Hundertwasser's goal was to reshape austere buildings by introducing irregular structures and vegetation in a harmonious fashion [6]. In the beginning of twentieth century, the British and North American garden city movement promote the integration of house and garden through features such as pergolas, trellis structures and self-clinging climbing plants. The green facade is constructed in the case of hanging or climbing plants alongside the wall, in which the direct green building's facade is the case in which the vegetation is directly attached to the wall, while indirect green building's facade consists of the supporting structure for vegetation [7]; which was improved in 1988 by the introduction of a stainless-steel cable system for green facades. The Modular Trellis Panel System was introduced to North America in the early 1990s. It consists of lightweight, galvanized, powder-coated steel panels that support plant growth. Designed to attach to building exteriors, it prevents direct vegetation contact with the structure. Their rigid design makes them ideal for freestanding green walls or bridging structures. Modular living walls trace their origins to earlier vertical greening systems. In 1938, Professor Stanley Hart White patented *Vegetation-Bearing Architectonic Structure and System*, marking the first known attempt at integrating vegetation into building facades. However, it wasn't until 1986 that French botanist Patrick Blanc, along with architect Adrien Fainsilber and engineer Peter Rice, successfully implemented the first indoor living wall. This innovation laid the groundwork for the modular living wall systems that we use today.

Figure 1: Patrick Blanc Vertical Garden "Halles Avignon", Provence, French Riviera, 2005. Available from: <https://www.verticalgardenpatrickblanc.com/node/1307> [accessed April 2, 2025]

Nowadays, the green wall that we see as the most spectacular and provocative in terms of art is Patrick Blanc's *Vegetative Mat Wall*. The living walls are built from materials like plastic, polystyrene, synthetic fabric and a metal structure that keeps it at distance of 5-10 cm from the wall surface so that plant material and water do not wet the wall canvas. A typical system includes a metal frame, a PVC layer, and an air gap, eliminating the need for soil. This design supports various species, such as perennials, ferns, and low shrubs, and adapts well to different climates. With automated irrigation and nutrient systems, maintenance is simplified. Obviously, the whole system is technically very well constructed and functional because it serves as a living thermal and sound insulation of the façade where is applied.

The aesthetic of green walls is defined by the variety of dynamic art compositions, diversity of planting material, but also many changes that during the annual vegetation cycle of those different plants are reflected in the overall appearance of the art composition. The plants used in a vertical garden are changing all the time: they green, grow and blossom, they sometimes change color due to temperature and time of the year. Such we get remarkable changes in overall sight of the very façade, during the year or decade. We consider them to be the latest version of murals, applicable in contemporary architecture (fig. 1). The old murals aesthetics have been overcome, which have become either a reminiscence of some classical or medieval style, that is, an association with antiquity, especially if one of the old techniques was used: such as a mosaic mural, tapestry, intarsia, ceramic panel, etc. This new type of living bio-mural such as vertical gardens abundant in various plant species meets the requirements of modern architecture regarding environmental standards and principles of sustainability.

Sustainability of green walls is, in terms of functionality, even more important for a contemporary architect. When used in interiors they significantly improve the quality of air providing more oxygen and air humidity in contrast to carbon dioxide and dried air with toxins harmful to inhale. The roots and plants eliminate toxins and filter the air. Thus, we provide a natural replacement for air purifiers and air conditioners. Already mentioned functions of thermal and sound insulation of exterior vertical gardens, complete the sustainability standards. Not to forget all the benefits it provides for human's health, from the fresh air and less sound and air pollution to the mental relaxation experienced watching the green and soft color and organic shapes of swaying leaves and branches.

Maybe even more popular than Blank's vertical gardens are vertical surfaces made of modules – Vertical Green Modules, or VGM. They can be both placed on facades or by interior walls as well as make free-standing vertical green forms. They could be used as a living passage or combined as an interesting complex area like a living green labyrinth, separate booth seating for gardens etc. The innovation of movable green walls for facades which panels change places or angles towards sun, can be opened or closed, are often used for walls windows and doors shading. They provide food-growing plantings and vertical gardening for occupiers of multistory prototype buildings, as well as maintaining habitat structures, for example, bird perches.[7]

Technological inventions mark aesthetical and functional improvement of green walls. As we can see, nowadays we have the whole range of different technologies and patents that can be used to create an interesting, useful and even more a visually precious green surface. From the point of view of wall decorative techniques, we can introduce such green surfaces as a new and necessary kind of contemporary *wall painting*. Like any older technological invention that changed the course and advanced the scope of art, the implementation of bio wall as a modern mural is provided by new technology. As a contemporary environmentalist-aesthetic claims, explaining the ways that art can help repair the damage we have done to the Planet: "Technologies are a tool, completely natural, adopted by humanity to extend its capabilities, in a process of growth and acceleration started in the Paleolithic period which opposed and guided natural selection with regard to our species. To limit the consequences of that impact or to put right damages, we will need more rather than less technologies in the future." [8] Implementing green murals in modern architectural projects, we fulfill both criteria of sustainability and applied art, ecology and aesthetics, where we combine nature with a technical approach to make use of the multiple benefits of green, forming a component of current urban design.

2.2. Ecological Sculpture

Considering the increasing aspiration of mankind to base production, economy and ecology on the principles of sustainable development, a huge number of spatial and ambient installations made of recycled material are present in contemporary art, as well as ecological sculptures that include scientific and technological patents based on renewable energy sources (solar, water and wind energy, etc.) On the other hand, some contemporary artists deal only with natural materials and structures, integrating, in such an indigenous way that sometimes reminds of children's game or primitive art and architecture, rough natural materials to new works of art. We can name this kind of artwork as *ecological sculptures* (fig. 2).

Ecological sculpture is a form of environmental art that integrates artistic expression with ecological principles. Its main goal is to create works that not only exist in harmony with nature but also actively contribute to the health and

sustainability of the environment. The key features of ecological sculpture are sustainability, functionality, site-specific form, the time-and-change factor and, often, community involvement. Mentioning sustainability, at the first place, it means that ecological sculptures often use natural, recycled, or biodegradable materials to reduce environmental impact. The functionality of eco-sculpture implies that many of them serve a dual purpose – art and function; for example, some sculptures may help purify water, provide habitat for wildlife, or prevent soil erosion. Ecological sculptures are site-specific which means that these works are usually designed with a specific location in mind, often responding to the natural landscape, local ecosystems, or cultural context. They usually change in time, considering their connection to nature or natural materials that are composed of. Many pieces are designed to evolve over time – to grow, decay, or transform with the natural elements. Ecological sculpture projects often involve the community, raising awareness about environmental issues and encouraging stewardship. Eco-sculptures are sometimes made of living plants. On the other hand, there are complex artworks that use wind, solar power, or water flow as part of their structure or function.

Figure 2: Mario Merz "Iglo di Petra (Igloo of Stone)", Kröller-Müller Museum, 1982.

Available at: <https://krollermuller.nl/en/conservation-of-igloo-di-pietra-by-mario-merz> [accessed April 11 2025]

For modern architecture we find it more suitable to visually communicate with those large ecological projects involving students and groups of designers and architects who seek a fashionable way to visualize human tendency towards eco-design refined by the spirit of elegance, aerodynamics and visual lightness that the taste of our time strives for. The works are produced using clean technology from renewable materials and are most often created as part of a wider project, competition or contest for the best design solutions for garden furniture, fountains, poles carrying solar lamps, chargers, and other gadgets needed by the modern passerby or consumer of these applied sculptures. A good example is the contemporary eco-sculpture designed by students during the eco-sculpture project in Dubai in 2024 (fig. 3). Such modern-design sculptures include not only aesthetics of elegance, some kind of perfection and technical innovation in their creation, but they also consider scientific approach to the very item of designing or topic they are referred to. For instance, creators sometimes embody the way physical invisible fields dwell or give form to a mathematical function or atomic structure creating the final form of their artwork. Both in the technology and aesthetics of these eco-sculptures, there is an undeniable connection between ecological ethics, art, and science.

Figure 3: "Ocean Soundwave Bench", Dubai, 2024. Available at: <https://www.gulftoday.ae/News/2024/04/24/Dubai-students-create-4-stunning-sustainable-art-sculptures> [accessed April 11 2025]

Renewable energy sculpture is an emerging facet of environmental art, developed in response to the growing urgency surrounding global climate change discussions. This practice is gaining momentum within both public sculpture and experimental architectural contexts. It typically involves a deliberate integration of functional elements, merging aesthetic expression with the operational aspects of energy production or saving. These projects are often the result of collaborative efforts among interdisciplinary teams, including design and engineering studios [13], and are typically tailored to specific architectural environments—an idea that connects to the topics discussed in the following subsection. Practitioners in this innovative field align their work with both ethical considerations and practical requirements, adhering to the standards set by Ecodesign principles.

2.3. Land Art in Landscape Architecture

Some scientists refer to land art as to the hypernym or the umbrella term of all the ecological art projects [3]. Even if it is questionable whether land art is the most omnipotent term to use for all ecologically oriented art, it is certain that it is the oldest and most significant form of it. There are different types of land art practices, such as Earth art or *Earthworks* or that certain land art which emphasizes the environment as an essential part of the artwork, as well as land art that cares about the overall well-being of the environment.

The very beginnings of land art, before it was presented to the public through the huge *Earthworks* of American land artists in the 60s and 70s of the twentieth century, start from the work of a Japanese-American artist Isama Noguchi on a project of children's playground. Noguchi's 1941 design for the Contoured Playground was an innovative playscape concept intended for Central Park in New York City (fig. 4). The design featured gentle earth mounds and abstract play structures, encouraging freeform play and exploration, as a response to earlier criticisms of his 1933 Play Mountain design, which was deemed too hazardous by city officials. Unfortunately, the onset of World War II halted the project's realization. [9] Noguchi's vision for playgrounds emphasized abstract forms and topographical variations, aiming to create spaces that fostered imagination and physical engagement. Although the *Contoured Playground* was never constructed, its concept has influenced modern playground design and is considered an early example of land art. [10]

Figure 4: Isama Noguchi, Contoured Playground, New York, USA, 1941. Nicholas Knight ©INFGM / ARS

An extraordinary and well-known example of park area created by a land artist is Nancy Holt's *Up and Under* realized in Pinsiö, Finland (fig. 5-6). It is a structure that consists of curved mound long 192 meters, inside which are placed several tunnels of length 74 m, with a diameter of 3 m, accompanied with reflective circle pulls of water besides the mound. It was commissioned by artist and farmer Osmo Rauhala as part of a broader initiative to restore and reclaim developed land. The sculpture consists of a curved, meandering mound of earth, featuring one vertical tunnel and seven horizontal tunnels aligned with the North Star, Polaris. Three reflective water pools are placed around the sculpture's base. The vertical tunnel offers a view of the sky above, while the earth beneath is sourced from various locations across Finland. The piece creates a landscape that invites both sensory exploration and thoughtful reflection. [11] Nowadays, it is an attractive place for visitors, art and nature lovers from all over the world.

Another of the most significant representatives of land art Richard Long created his works often in agreement with prehistoric forms on the sites of Irish shrines, circularly arranged holy stones and labyrinths. His art basically has freedom of movement as a premise of artistic action, more precisely walking as the beginning of artistic reflection and land-art creation. "A walk expresses space and freedom and the knowledge of it can live in the imagination of anyone, and that is another space too", he claims [12]. In this conjunction of human body and nature, of movement and freedom, Long created most of his works that open the possibility to be revisited and appropriated by other artists, designers and landscape architects as parts of interactive spots for children play and investigations in children's playgrounds, kindergartens etc. Many of passages, climbing frames and huts in specific natural sites for children's recreation and outdoor activities are spontaneously made by land-artists who wanted to enrich and make the children's space for movement, exercise, exploring and interaction with nature more interesting.

Considering the need for more green areas and natural spaces for children play both in the country as well as in the cities, we find it necessary to incorporate projects of landscape architects and green architecture designers in symbiosis with land-artists and inventive designers of eco-friendly sculptures to create multipurposed contemporary parks and playgrounds meeting the standards of sustainable society. Multidisciplinary approach of architecture, science: ecology, botany, physics, anatomy, ecological education, etc. and environmental art, specifically, land art is needed to construct areas where body, mind, and soul could be satisfied with both healthy, peaceful but also inventive, investigation and play inspirational spaces.

Figure 5-6: Nancy Holt *Up and Under*, Pinsiö, Finland, 1987-98. Available from: <https://holtsmithsonfoundation.org/and-under>

Landscape architecture that plans integrate works of land art in modern green areas of cities should be engaged of given freedom to express and embody their creations in a larger and more complex projects of green areas, as well as groups of designers that create inventive and complex patents that use renewable energy sources, sometimes interactive with people who use that amusement parks for play and fun. Such inventive projects can be seen in the biennale in design competitions, inviting architects, artists, engineers and landscape architects from around the world to submit works of public art that also produce clean energy, led by the *Land Art Generator Initiative* in Australia. [13] Many of winning projects integrate plants, green surfaces, sculptural solar panels, form that recall indigenous art of the area but also interact with the landscape of future. The variety of ideas and perfection of sublime unity of form and usability together with fulfilment of the energy zero request of the context, recommend these projects for worldwide application. Still, if we want it to be rougher and more nature alike, connected to the reminiscence of primitive art and spontaneity of children's games in materials, architect will choose the right landscape artist to promote the worths of a hand-made unique work of art in specific site.

Works of land art or earthworks are interactive and evoke spirit of curiosity and investigation in children. They communicate with both the landscape and surroundings as well as with the people they are made for, who pass by, or through them, climb them, hide and seek and altogether play with them also witnessing changes made during the course of year and atmospheric conditions, or through longer period of time. The specificity of an exceptional landscape architecture solution may stem not only from its functionality and carefully considered conceptual design, but also from the implementation of a piece of land art whose uniqueness and peculiarity radiates and captivates the landscape.

3. CONCLUSION

Trying to profound the seek for the best measure of utility and aesthetics in the emerging objects of green architecture design, we recommend the implementation of unique artworks by ecologically oriented artists in the fields of bio-walls, eco-sculpture, and land art. We recognize the green wall in its most luxurious form—designed by Patrick Blanc—as a tapestry or green mural applicable to both interiors and exteriors of buildings, as well as VGM, which can be seen as free-standing, three-dimensional green forms.

Eco-sculpture is applicable in contemporary architecture, serving as public sculpture, renewable energy sculpture—with a practical function of saving or producing energy for gadgets—and as sculptural forms that function as park furniture or playground elements.

Land art, which emerged from artists' protests against commercial and possessive perspectives on artworks, could, in future landscape architecture, provide public earthworks that serve everyone—especially children and nature lovers. Thus, these works are no longer isolated or located far from civilization, but are close to and useful for a wider audience.

Land artists, together with urban and landscape architects, designers, and inventors, should find innovative ways to enhance newly created land art projects by using renewable energy, incorporating technological inventions, and developing sustainable and applicable green-energy design solutions.

The integration of all these forms of art within the architectural concept of a "kindergarten without boundaries"—a place for children that is naturally immersed in its environment—should be opened as a new topic in contemporary architecture. This new concept of green architecture, together with forms of environmental art, should become part of a broader agenda supporting ecologically oriented education, and thus serve as a bridge to planetary restoration based on principles of sustainability.

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